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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MEDiterranean Grape, OLive and Durum wheat** food systems

Deliverable 7.4

Report on Quality control, documentation repository, and knowledge management n.2

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable documents the updated data, quality and knowledge management plans of the MED-GOLD project. It discusses and presented the outcomes of the Quality Management Plan after being applied over the Months 19-36 of MED-GOLD and provides updates on aspects of this plan. Finally, it discusses and updates the rules of the MED-GOLD Knowledge Management Plan. Through this reporting, the deliverable outlines the experience gained so far regarding data, quality and knowledge management.

1. OBJECTIVES

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartB Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

2. IMPACT

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimised risk	X
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	X
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value added climate services in potential end-user markets	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

3. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Concept / Term	Definition
N/A	

4. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Acronym	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
DoA	Description of Activities
GA	Grand Agreement
MED-GOLD	The project entitled "Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MED iterranean G rape, O Live and D urum wheat food systems"

5. REFERENCES

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date

6. DETAILED REPORT

The Quality Plan is the document setting out the quality assurance procedures for the MED-GOLD project. Its aim is to assure that the results and deliverables of the project are of high quality and meet the specifications set in the project Description of Work. Once accepted by the Consortium, this Quality Plan becomes an official project document, which should govern all partners' and consortium's actions. This deliverable reports on the results and outcomes of the Months 19-36.

6.1. STATE OF THE ART

The Quality Plan is to be used by:

- All Consortium Partners, responsible for preparing and amending deliverables,
- Quality Experts, responsible for reviewing completed quality plans and sign-off,
- Any responsible person of a Consortium Partner for approving works to be done by third parties, in order to complete deliverables.

6.2 MED-GOLD Quality Assurance

6.2.1 PREPARATION OF MED-GOLD DELIVERABLES

MED-GOLD Quality Plan is applicable to all the activities, which are related to the project. Hence, compliance of its execution with the Quality Plan is mandatory for all involved.

The Consortium quality policy is as follows:

- To implement and maintain a quality system,
- To identify for all involved their responsibilities regarding quality,
- To ensure that all deliverables comply with the contract.

During the reporting period M19-M36 of MED-GOLD and for the preparation of the project deliverables, we followed the time-schedule described in Quality Plan (ANNEX A). According to this time-schedule, a complete draft of the deliverable is submitted for Quality Assessment (QA) that aims to ensure its top quality and, at the very minimum, its compliance with the relevant contractual obligations set out in the Description of Action (DoA) document, and the documentation standards of the partners of the MED-GOLD consortium. In all cases we followed an approach that involves two Quality Experts and the Quality Manager for the review of each deliverable. In case of a technical deliverable, the quality experts involved researchers that have a technical background and the same time a user/business background, while in case of a business-oriented deliverable, the reverse setup was used. After reviewing the deliverable, both Quality Experts had to fill-in a Quality Assurance Review form (ANNEX B) that contains questions about the quality of the deliverable in terms of coverage, technical content, evaluation and innovation, and presentation, as presented in the MED-GOLD Quality plan. Based on this feedback, the authors of the deliverable produced the final version of the document that was then submitted to the EC.

Following this plan, we prepared and submitted 13 MED-GOLD deliverables of the project on time (which were due during the reporting period (M19-M36) of the project's lifetime). The submitted deliverables are presented in Table 1 below. The same methodology will be followed by the project consortium concerning the preparation and submission of the remaining project deliverables until the end of the project, unless currently unforeseen reasons introduce the need for a modification or adaptation of this plan.

Table 1: List of MED-GOLD submitted and reviewed deliverable

Del No	Deliverable name	WP No	Lead Partner	Quality Reviewed	Date of submission	Comments
D2.2	Report on the tool performance	2	ec2ce	YES	M30	N/A

D2.7	Second Feedback report from users on olive oil pilot service development	2	NOA	YES	M28	N/A
D3.2	Report on the methodology followed to implement the wine pilot services	3	BSC	YES	M30	N/A
D3.7	Second Feedback report from users on wine pilot service development	3	BSC	YES	M28	N/A
D4.2	Design of innovative agro-climatic systems for durum wheat	4	JRC	YES	M30	N/A
D4.7	Second Feedback report from users on durum wheat pilot service development	1	JRC	YES	M28	N/A
D6.2	Co-designed Climate Services Communication and Exploitation Indicators Report n.1	6	UTH	YES	M24	N/A
D6.3	Dissemination and Capacity Building Materials n.1	6	BSC	YES	M24	N/A
D6.4	Science-based knowledge relevant for Climate related Policies n.1	6	CNR	YES	M24	N/A
D6.4	Compilation of Publications Abstracts n.1	6	UNILEEDS	YES	M24	N/A
D6.6	Summer training event n.1	6	ENEA	YES	M30	N/A
D6.11	Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report n.2	6	MET-OFFICE	YES	M24	N/A
D6.22	Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities n.2	6	GMV	YES	M24	N/A

6.2.2 OVERALL MED-GOLD PROGRESS AND COMPLIANCE WITH TIMEPLAN

The overall progress of MED-GOLD according to the contractual obligations, and its compliance with the timeplan for fulfilling these obligations, is based on the list of project milestones (see Table 2). Based on coordinated activities by all WPs and MED-GOLD partners, and with the help of the established communication plan, the members of the MED-GOLD Executive Board evaluated the compliance of the project's progress with this pre-defined time-plan.

The outcomes of this effort include successfully reaching the 1 milestone of MED-GOLD.

Table 2: List of Milestones

N	Name	Responsible	Month	Comment
9	Data management check and update	ENEA	M24	The DMP has been updated during the First project review phase and the IPR matrix (https://drive.google.com/open?id=1InhQOKk2WamsiHcIdjwL54_nDf6dN4OmK1bxly_has) has been also further updated in the GA 2019, held in Cagliari 15-17 October 2019. A first list of the MEDGOLD products with the related licences have been included in the IPR matrix that will be continuously updated as new products will be available.

6.2.3 STATUS OF MED-GOLD KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

In the table 3 below, we presented the status of the MED-GOLD KPIs.

Table 3. Status of the project KPIs

Item	KPI and target value	KPI Status
MED-GOLD website	About 5,000 user sessions per year (data to be collected through Google analytics or similar systems). The website will be maintained for at least one year after the termination of the project.	9066 Total User sessions (2018 - 31 May 2020) 4716 sessions (Feb 2018 - to 30 Nov 2019) 21months - 224 sessions/month 4350 sessions (30 Nov 2019 to 31 May 2020) 6 months - 483 sessions/month Increasing rate: 115% 5163 users 1.8 sessions/user
MED-GOLD Twitter		165235 impressions 2978 engagements 465 retweets 859 likes 392 followers (since beginning of the project)
Stakeholders' database	A list of about 500 stakeholders involved in agrifood-related domains, policy- and decision makers, academia, regional/local authorities, industry, investors, etc.	MED-GOLD Community Members: 170 Academic Network: 35 Initiative related to Climate Services: 14 Agriculture services: 10 Potential initiatives contacted: 26 Policy makers contacted: 8
eNewsletters and contents (articles, press releases, infosheets)	Two eNewsletter released per year targeting a community of 500 stakeholders (to be reached at the end of the project). Distribution of at least 6 press and news releases and at least 4 articles/interviews to the general and specialised media, portals, blogs and promoted via social media with hundreds of take-ups each. Six infosheets available on the website, distributed via social media and through 1-to-1 direct mailing to the specific target groups.	INFO SHEET: 4 (Translated to 6 languages) Newsletter: 3 Press article: 1 News: 55 PODCASTS: 4 Press release: 25
Handout materials	MED-GOLD flyer and e-handbook will be both browsable through the website and available in printable format for public download. The flyer in English and in local languages will be printed and distributed during the events.	Flyer: 1

Participation in conferences	MED-GOLD will target the participation in 10 major international conferences events (fairs, conferences, exhibitions, etc.) in the course of the project.	Conference participation: 26
Events (online & off-line)	3 webinars will be organised. Expected participants: minimum 30 per webinar. Organisation of a final event with stakeholders (format to be decided) at the end of the project to present the project's results.	<p>WEBINAR: 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate services as drivers of value into the Mediterranean wine sector Attendees: 18 - What are the time scales of climate services for agriculture? Attendees: 90 <p>LIVING LAB: 1 (19 ATTENDEES)</p> <p>MED-GOLD WORKSHOPS: 5</p> <p>SECTORAL WORKSHOP (around 10-15 participants for each workshop)</p> <p>1 Open workshop for local community in Porto in 2018 (around 15 participants) + 1 Open workshop for local community in Cagliari in 2019 (around 40 participants)</p>
Use of partners' network	MED-GOLD will take advantage of the partners' existing communication channels and networks to disseminate and communicate its results. Examples are the partners' newsletters, their websites and platforms, their social media accounts and magazines. Outreach: 2000-3000 users	<p>During the main outreach event (e.g. General Assembly in Cagliari) the project has profited from existing communication channels provided by BeeToBit to broadcast the workshop with local stakeholders (see material collected here: https://www.med-gold.eu/it/documenti-pubblicazioni/). The existing network of BSC has been instrumental in engaging participants in the webinars. All main news concerning the MED-GOLD activities have been channelled through the CLIMATEUROPE network thanks to the direct engagement of BSC and UKMO with this action.</p> <p>The industrial partners DCOOP and SOGRAPE and the service provider HORTA have been very active in disseminating the project activities and results through their communication channels.</p> <p>Overall, considering the number of clients/partners of the industrial stakeholders and service providers, the large network of the main scientific partners and the catalyzing effect of the local workshop in Cagliari (October 2019) we estimate that the planned target of 2000-3000 users have been already reached during this second reporting period.</p>
Mobilization of Stakeholder Associations, support from the Advisory Board members and other EU projects and initiatives	Associations provide direct communication channels into the target groups the MED- GOLD is trying to penetrate. These include all the associations and initiatives the partners are members of, as well as the members of the Advisory Board. Besides that, other EU initiatives providing communication support to EU funded projects as well as other EU funded projects will be	<p>ADVISORY BOARD MEMBERS: 12 members. 5 members have participated in the project's General Assembly, 1 member has contributed to the Living Lab 2020, 7 members have provided a contribution to our website and news stream.</p> <p>Mobilized stakeholder Associations: Union for the Mediterranean, COPA-COGECA, the Spanish Ministry, CEEV and the Catalan Water Agency.</p>

	approached to exploit synergies and jointly organized actions.	
Scientific/technical publications	The target is 10 scientific papers in high impact journals, and 10 scientific papers in high- reputation International Conferences.	Scientific/technical Publications: 13 Publications supported under Open Access and uploaded at Zenodo.
Participants satisfaction	Qualitative information on the satisfaction of participants to MED-GOLD events	LIVING LAB 2020: (https://www.surveymonkey.co.uk/r/MED-GOLDlivinglab)

6.3 MED-GOLD Knowledge management

A set of established rules related to the management of knowledge and intellectual property in the MED-GOLD was documented in the MED-GOLD Consortium Agreement (CA). These conventions (which are discussed and extended in the following section) aim to ensure the protection of confidential information and patenting of important knowledge that will be created during the project's lifetime.

6.3.1 MED-GOLD KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT PLAN

The MED-GOLD consortium, further to the Consortium Agreement is working on IPR and Knowledge management plan and created a live “matrix” collecting all relevant information on the above issues (see ANNEX C, presented more in detail in the DMP D7.2)

In summary, the main principles are listed below:

Aiming to establish a management plan regarding the extracted knowledge and the created Intellectual Property (IP) assets during the project, the consortium has defined the following set of definitions:

- **Foreground:** the project results, including information, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated by the project. Such results include rights related to copyright; design rights; patent rights; or similar forms of protection.
- **Ownership:** Foreground resulting from the project is owned by the participant generating it. When Foreground is generated jointly (i.e. where the separate parts of some result cannot be attributed to different participants), it will be jointly owned, unless the participants concerned agree on a different solution. In the case of “Joint Foreground”, each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Foreground on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s), and each of the joint owners shall be entitled to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties, without any right to sub-license, subject to conditions that include fair and reasonable compensation being provided to the other joint owner(s); these conditions are specified in the CA.
- **Protection:** valuable Foreground will be protected by its owner(s) through filing of patent applications where possible, or other Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection measures. The parties undertake not to leave valuable foreground unprotected. No public disclosure of Foreground will take place before a decision is made regarding its possible protection.
- **Background:** this refers to background information that is held by Parties prior to their accession to the Grant Agreement, as well as copyrights or other IPRs pertaining to such information, the application for which has been filed before their accession to the Grant Agreement, and which is needed to carry out the Project or for using the Foreground. Each Party shall remain the owner of its own background.
- **Access rights:** access rights to another participant's Foreground or Background will only be granted if the requesting participant needs that access in order to carry out the project or to use in its own foreground. The details pertaining to access rights have been specified in the CA. Rights pertaining to joint exploitation activities will be agreed upon between the partners in separate Business Agreements.

Based on this group of rules, we crafted an initial record of all IP assets that will be created in the different work packages of the project, so that attention can be given to the protection of the most valuable IP by means of patents or other methods, while ensuring that no ethics requirements are being violated in any case. The identified IP assets are reported in detail in the internal “matrix” created.

6.4 CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable, the updated Quality and Knowledge Management Plan of MED-GOLD was reported. In terms of Quality Management, the outcomes of the foreseen procedures related to the preparation of the project deliverables and the compliance of the project with the determined timeplan were discussed. Finally, in terms of Knowledge Management, the rules were presented and the on-going work reported.

ANNEX A. ANNEX

QUALITY MANAGEMENT PLAN

LINK TO [ANNEX A](#)

ANNEX A.

QUALITY ASSURANCE REVIEW FORM

Link to [Annex B](#)

ANNEX B.

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHT ACCESS MATRIX SCHEME

Link to [Annex C](#)

END OF DOCUMENT

